

Isolation and characterisation of cobalt(II)-reduced glutathione complex

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The cobalt(II)-glutathione complex has been synthesized in the aqueous medium and its composition has been determined by elemental and thermogravimetric analysis. Binding modes have been determined by IR and ^1H NMR spectroscopy and electronic spectral studies. The complex has a square-planar geometry.

Glutathione, γ -glutamyl-cysteinyl-glycine is a physiologically abundant tripeptide. It is a multidentate ligand having O, N and S (thiolate) as coordinating sites. Studies on the interaction of cobalt with glutathione is interesting as cobalt has to be transported to the storage domain through the GSH rich environment¹. Herein, the isolation of Co^{II} -GSH complex and the assessment of the metal-peptide environment are reported to understand the reaction pattern.

Results and discussion

Thermogravimetric analysis : Indicates the presence of four H_2O in lattice site per molecule of the complex.

FTIR spectral study : The symmetric and antisymmetric stretching frequencies of the NHCO group are observed at 3345 and 3253 cm^{-1} respectively in the GSH². These two bands are buried under a broad envelope appeared because of the presence of H_2O molecule in the complex. The shifting of the 1642(sh) cm^{-1} of $>\text{CONH}$ stretching vibration of amide I to 1655.8 cm^{-1} indicates the involvement of the amide I group of the GSH in complexation with cobalt through oxygen atom³. The blue-shift of this vibration occurs due to the electronic redistribution of the ligand atom after complexation. Other vibrations for amide groups at 3345 and 3253 cm^{-1} are buried under the broad envelope because of H_2O molecule.

A very weak band appears at 1736.2 cm^{-1} and the symmetric stretching vibration of COO^- at 1414.1 cm^{-1} as a very weak band in the complex. These findings support the proposition of the linkage of COO^- group through deprotonation^{3,4}. The appearance of a strong band at 608 cm^{-1} indicates the formation of Co-S linkage³. The above mentioned linkages as proposed by FTIR studies have been verified by ^1H NMR spectroscopy as well.

^1H NMR spectral study : The peak positions with their

assignments⁵ are summarized in Table 1. The glycyl H_α proton signal is formed as a triplet in GSH but in the complex this signal has been reduced to a doublet with simultaneous shifting. This implies the coordination of gly $>\text{CO}$ with cobalt. The drastic change in the glu H_γ signal after complexation, indicates the participation of vicinal glutamate amide group in coordination. The chemical shift of the glu H_α is indicative of the linkage of α -glutamyl- NH_2 group. The change in the glu H_β signal is a result of the overall electrometric effect because of the coordination of the groups attached with vicinal glu α and glu γ carbon centers.

Table 1

GSH	Co-GSH	Assignment	Comments	
2.033	1.901 _d	Glu H_β	Glu amides linkage and Glu- NH_2 linkage (electromeric effect)	
2.057 _q	2.060			
2.080				
2.104				
2.428	2.413 _d	Glu H_α	Glu amide linkage	
2.452 _q	2.425			
2.459				
2.459				
2.831	Broadened to quarters 2.809 to 2.886 3.119 to 3.116	Cys H_β	Cys-S linkage	
2.853				
3.708	3.648 _d	Gly H_α	Gly-CO linkage	
3.729 _t	3.683			
3.750				
3.879	3.768	Glu H_α	Glu NH_2 linkage	
4.446	Buried in the H_2O	Cys H_α		
4.466 _t				
4.486				

Electronic absorption spectroscopic study : Two peaks are observed at 467 (ϵ_{max} 90) and 399 (ϵ_{max} 120) nm. This indicates a square planar geometry for the complex.

Magnetochemical study : The magnetic moment of the compound is 2.87 B.M.

EPR study : The EPR spectrum of the compound shows g_1 , g_2 and g_3 values of the complex to be 2.217, 2.145 and 2.015 respectively. Both magnetochemical and EPR studies support square planar geometry around cobalt(II) centre.

Experimental

Materials : Glutathione (GSH) reduced (SRL) and other chemicals of analar quality were used in the experiment.

Preparation of cobalt-glutathione complex : To 300 mg (0.5 mM) GSH reduced dissolved in 5 ml water, 280 mg (0.5 mM) cobalt sulfate ($\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$) dissolved in 5 ml water was added portionwise with constant stirring. pH was maintained at 6.5 by added NaOH solution. Stirring continued for 30–35 min and 50 ml of isopropyl alcohol added when a brown ppt. was obtained. It was cooled for 1 h, filtered, washed with isopropanol and ether and dried in vacuo. It was recrystallized, when shining brown powder obtained. Yield 0.28 g (48%). Only one spot is obtained in thin layer chromatographic separation. Elemental analysis were carried out with Perkin-Elmer 240C Elemental Analyser. Several attempts to grow diffractable grade crystals were abortive. Analysis : found (calcd.) Co, 12.95 (12.88); N, 8.86 (9.17); S, 6.81 (6.98).

FTIR was recorded (KBr) in Perkin-Elmer RFX-I, electronic spectra in Hitachi u 3410, NMR in Bruker DPX-300

spectrometers. EPR in Varian E-112 spectrometer and TG in Shimadzu-DT-30 TG analyzer.

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References

1. V. Shi, J. Berglund and L. I. Edding, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1996, **35**, 3498; M. Danfour, C. J. Schorah and S. W. Evans, *Immunopharmacol-Immunotoxicol*, 1999, **21**, 277.
2. R. M. Silverstein, O. G. Bassler and T. C. Morrill, "Spectrophotometric Identification of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1974.
3. B. S. Garg, D. N. Kumar and B. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 1205; K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compound", 2nd ed., Wiley, 1978; B. Odenheimer and W. Wolf, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, **66**, L41.
4. S. T. Chow, C. A. McAuliffe and B. T. Sayle, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 451.
5. S. J. Berners-Price and P. W. J. Kuchel, *J. Inorg. Biochim.*, 1990, **38**, 305; A. Corazza, L. Harvey and P. J. Sadler, *Eur. J. Biochim.*, 1996, **236**, 697.